

Original article

Ecological footprint of cassava mill effluent: Implications for soil microbiology and physicochemical integrity

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Abstract

Background: Cassava processing generates large volumes of effluent that can significantly alter soil ecosystems. The discharge of untreated cassava mill effluent into the environment is a growing concern due to its potential to disrupt soil microbiological balance and physicochemical integrity. **Objectives:** This study aimed to assess the ecological impact of cassava mill effluent on soil by evaluating changes in microbial diversity, abundance, and physicochemical properties, with a view to understanding the environmental and health implications of such contamination. **Materials and Methods:** Soil samples were collected from three sites (A–C), including areas impacted by cassava effluent. Microbial diversity and abundance were determined through culture-based isolation techniques. Bacterial and fungal isolates were identified and quantified. Physicochemical parameters such as pH, nitrogen, potassium, phosphorus, and heavy metal concentrations were also analyzed. Additionally, antibiotic susceptibility testing was performed on selected microbial isolates. **Results:** Impacted soil showed an elevated bacterial count (7.8×10^5 cfu/g) dominated by *Bacillus* sp. and *Pseudomonas* sp. (28.6%), while fungal growth was suppressed, with *Penicillium* sp. (27.2%) being the most prevalent among fungi. The physicochemical analysis revealed significant changes in soil chemistry, with increased nitrogen (797 mg/L), potassium (459 mg/L), and phosphorus (432 mg/L) levels. Heavy metals such as copper and iron were present in concentrations that may pose toxicity risks. Antibiotic testing indicated the presence of resistant strains, with *Bacillus* sp. showing resistance to several antibiotics, although Ciprofloxacin was most effective. **Conclusion:** Cassava mill effluent enriches the soil with nutrients that stimulate bacterial growth but also leads to reduced fungal diversity, acidification, heavy metal accumulation, and the emergence of antibiotic-resistant microorganisms. These findings highlight the need for urgent and sustainable effluent management strategies to prevent long-term environmental degradation and protect public health.

Keywords: Cassava Mill Effluent; Environmental Impact; Soil Contamination Soil Microbiology; Soil Physicochemistry;

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Introduction

Cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) is a major staple crop cultivated extensively across tropical regions, especially in Africa, Asia, and Latin America. Renowned for its high carbohydrate content (approximately 85.9%) and low protein levels (about 1.3%), cassava serves as a critical food source for millions, particularly among low-income populations in developing countries. Despite its nutritional value, cassava contains cyanogenic glucosides—compounds that release toxic hydrogen cyanide upon hydrolysis—posing health risks when improperly processed.^{1,2}

Introduced from South America to Africa in the 16th century, cassava has since become deeply

integrated into the diets and economies of sub-Saharan African nations. Nigeria, in particular, stands as the world's leading producer of cassava, driven by the widespread consumption of processed products such as *garri*, a fermented and roasted form of cassava flour.^{3,4} This rise in demand has spurred the rapid growth of cassava processing industries, especially small- to medium-scale enterprises, many of which are situated within residential and peri-urban areas.^{5,6}

However, the traditional methods used in cassava processing generate significant volumes of liquid and solid waste, including cyanide-rich effluent, organic matter, and suspended solids. These waste products are often discharged directly into the surrounding environment without adequate treatment. Such practices have led to the contamination of farmlands, surface water bodies, and groundwater reserves, resulting in adverse effects on soil health, aquatic ecosystems, and public health.⁷⁻⁹

Previous studies have demonstrated that cassava mill effluent (CME) can hinder seed germination, alter microbial communities, and degrade physicochemical properties of soil due to its high acidity, cyanide content, and nutrient imbalance.^{10,11} These findings underscore the urgent need for systematic investigation into the environmental consequences of cassava effluent disposal. Addressing this issue through scientific inquiry and policy-driven waste management strategies is critical for safeguarding ecosystem sustainability and human well-being.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

This study was carried out at the **Department of Human Nutrition and Dietetics, Federal University of Health Sciences, Azare**, located in **Bauchi State, North-Eastern Nigeria**. Soil samples were obtained from cassava mill effluent dump sites situated in two Local Government Areas (LGAs) within the state—**Bauchi and Katagum**—both known for significant cassava processing activities. These locations were selected based on their active use and observable environmental exposure to cassava effluent.

Experimental Details

Sample Collection and Preparation

Soil samples were aseptically collected from **three cassava mill effluent disposal sites**, designated as Sites A, B, and C, across the selected locations. At each site, samples were obtained at two distances from the point of effluent discharge: **5 meters**, representing the impacted zone, and **50 meters**,

serving as the control site with minimal exposure. Samples were carefully transferred into sterile, ice-cooled containers to inhibit microbial activity during transportation to the laboratory for immediate analysis.

Serial Dilution and Inoculation

In the laboratory, each soil sample underwent a **serial dilution process**. A **0.1 mL aliquot** from the appropriate dilution was inoculated into **nutrient agar (NA)** for bacterial isolation and **potato dextrose agar (PDA)** for fungal cultivation. All inoculations were performed in **triplicate** to ensure accuracy. Bacterial cultures were incubated at **37°C for 24 hours**, while fungal cultures were incubated at **ambient room temperature (25–28°C) for 5 to 7 days**, in accordance with standard microbiological protocols (Cheesbrough, 2005; Okoye, 2020).

Microbial Characterization and Identification

Distinct colonies were subcultured to obtain pure isolates, which were then characterized based on **cultural appearance, microscopic morphology**, and a series of **biochemical tests**. These tests included **Gram staining, motility, oxidase, catalase, citrate utilization, indole production, methyl red**, and **Voges-Proskauer** reactions. Identification was carried out using standard microbiological guidelines (Fawole & Oso, 2004; Cheesbrough, 2005; Okoye, 2020).

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics, including simple ratios and percentages, were employed to summarize the distribution of microbial isolates. Differences in microbial counts between sample groups were analyzed using **Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)** to determine statistically significant variations across independent groups.

Results:

Sample Overview

A total of three soil samples were analyzed: two obtained from cassava mill effluent-contaminated sites and one from unimpacted, agriculturally fertile soil, which served as the control. Microbiological assessments confirmed the presence of diverse bacterial and fungal communities across the samples.

Bacterial Isolates

The predominant bacterial species isolated included:

Bacillus sp. – 28.6%; *Pseudomonas* sp. – 28.6%; *Corynebacterium* sp. – 14.3%; *Escherichia coli* – 14.2%; *Enterobacter* sp. – 7.1%; *Proteus* sp. – 7.1%

Fungal Isolates

The fungal community was represented by the following isolates:

Penicillium sp. - 27.2%; *Aspergillus* sp. - 18.2%; *Candida* sp. - 18.2%; *Saccharomyces* sp. - 18.2%; *Mucor* sp. - 9.1%; *Rhizopus* sp. - 9.1%

Microbial Enumeration

Quantitative microbial analysis is summarized in **Figure 1**. The **mean heterotrophic bacterial counts** across the samples were as follows:

Control soil (unimpacted): $7.0 \pm 0.11 \times 10^5$ cfu/g;

Effluent soil: $5.1 \pm 0.28 \times 10^5$ cfu/g ;

Polluted/impacted soil: $7.8 \pm 0.19 \times 10^5$ cfu/g

The **fungal counts** for the same samples were:

Control soil: $4.2 \pm 0.57 \times 10^5$ cfu/g; Effluent soil: $4.4 \pm 0.41 \times 10^5$ cfu/g;

Polluted/impacted soil: $3.9 \pm 0.42 \times 10^5$ cfu/g

Overall, the highest bacterial load was observed in the impacted soil, with a count of $7.8 \pm 0.19 \times 10^5$ cfu/g, while fungal counts remained consistently lower than bacterial counts across all soil samples. This suggests that cassava mill effluent promotes bacterial proliferation more than fungal growth.

Physico-Chemical Analysis of Cassava Effluent and Soil Samples

The physico-chemical properties of cassava mill effluent, cassava-impacted soil, and un-impacted (control) soil were analyzed, and the results are summarized in **Table 1**. Each parameter was measured in duplicate, and statistical analysis was conducted using **One-Way ANOVA** at a **95% confidence level (p < 0.05)** to determine significant differences among the sample groups.

pH and Nutrient Composition

The **cassava effluent** exhibited a strongly **acidic pH** of **3.13**, while the **un-impacted soil** and **impacted soil** had **slightly alkaline pH** values of **7.87** and **7.21**, respectively. Nitrogen concentration was markedly highest in the effluent sample (**797.00 mg/L**), compared to **95.15 mg/L** in un-impacted soil and **7.51 mg/L** in impacted soil. **Potassium levels** also followed a similar trend, with significantly higher values recorded in the effluent than in both soil samples.

Metal Concentrations and Additional Parameters

Magnesium concentrations were comparable between the cassava effluent (**657.75 mg/L**) and the impacted soil (**660.85 mg/L**), but were significantly lower in the un-impacted soil (**36.95 mg/L**). **Calcium, sodium, and electrical conductivity** were found to be elevated in both the cassava effluent and un-impacted soil when compared to the impacted soil.

The **biological oxygen demand (BOD₅)** was highest in the impacted soil (**7.18 mg/L**), followed by the effluent (**5.73 mg/L**) and un-impacted soil (**4.54 mg/L**), indicating a higher organic load and microbial activity in the impacted site. **Total dissolved solids (TDS)** were greatest in the cassava effluent (**478.75 mg/L**) and lowest in the impacted soil, reflecting effluent solute richness.

Figure 1 Bacterial and fungal counts at the impacted soil, un-impacted soil and cassava effluent (A Impacted soil, B - Un-impacted soil and C - Cassava effluent)

Figure 2 The sensitivity of different gram negative organisms and antibiotics

Figure 3 The sensitivity of different gram positive organisms and antibiotics

Heavy Metals and Nitrogenous Compounds

Among heavy metals, **copper concentrations** in the cassava effluent were **2 to 3 times higher** than those found in both soil samples. **Iron, cobalt, and ammonia** were also most concentrated in the effluent, signaling potential environmental toxicity risks. **Zinc levels** remained relatively consistent across all samples.

In terms of nitrogenous compounds, **nitrate** levels peaked in the effluent (**12.01 mg/L**), whereas **nitrite** levels were highest in the un-impacted soil (**88.05 mg/L**), possibly due to differential microbial nitrification activity.

Statistical Significance and Antibiotic Susceptibility Testing

All values reported as means ± standard deviation were subjected to **One-Way ANOVA**, and

statistically significant differences between sample groups were denoted using superscript letters *a*, *b*, and *c* ($p < 0.05$). The symbol **BDLd** indicates values **below the detection limit**.

Antibiotic Susceptibility Profiles

Figures 2 and 3 present the **antibiotic susceptibility patterns** of Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria isolated from cassava effluent-contaminated and control soil samples. The test panel included 16 antibiotics: **Streptomycin, Ciporex, Ampicillin, Tarivid, Nalidixic Acid, Peflacin, Gentamicin, Augmentin, Ciprofloxacin, Septrin, Levofloxacin, Ampiclox, Rifampin, Amoxil, Norfloxacin, and Erythromycin.**

Target organisms included **Pseudomonas sp., Proteus sp., and Escherichia coli**, isolated from both impacted and unimpacted sites.

Key Findings

1. **Ciprofloxacin** demonstrated the highest efficacy, producing inhibition zones of **25 mm** for *Pseudomonas* sp. and **24 mm** for *Escherichia coli*.
2. **Tarivid** and **Septin** showed the **lowest effectiveness**, with inhibition zones of just **6 mm** for *Pseudomonas* sp., *E. coli*, and *Proteus* sp.
3. *Pseudomonas* sp. from effluent-impacted soil showed heightened sensitivity to most antibiotics tested.
4. Among Gram-positive bacteria, **Bacillus** sp. isolated from effluent-contaminated soil exhibited the highest zone of inhibition (**24 mm**) with Ciprofloxacin.

Overall Antibiotic Performance

Levofloxacin, **Streptomycin**, and **Gentamicin** exhibited moderate efficacy, with inhibition zones ranging from **10 mm to 20 mm**. Other antibiotics showed variable activity, with inhibition zones ranging from **6 mm to 24 mm**.

Dominant Microbial Species

Bacillus sp. was the most frequently isolated bacterium across all study sites. *Corynebacterium* sp. and *Enterobacter* sp. followed in prevalence

Discussion Microbial Diversity and Abundance

The study confirmed the presence of a wide array of microbial species, including six bacterial and eleven fungal genera. The dominance of *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Penicillium* species aligns with findings from previous studies.^{1,2}

Microbial Load Comparisons

The highest bacterial count was recorded in cassava effluent-impacted soil ($7.8 \pm 0.19 \times 10^5$ cfu/g), whereas fungal populations were consistently lower across all samples. These trends corroborate earlier studies indicating the suppressive effect of acidic effluent on fungal growth.³

Impact of Cassava Effluent on Soil Ecology

While effluent-enhanced nutrient levels supported bacterial growth, the acidic pH and toxic cyanogenic compounds negatively influenced overall microbial diversity. Non-impacted soil exhibited a more balanced microbial ecosystem, suggesting the degradative effects of cassava effluent on soil health, consistent with prior findings.⁴⁻⁶

Conclusion

This study underscores the **dual impact** of cassava mill effluent: it promotes certain bacterial proliferation while **degrading soil quality**, altering microbial diversity, and introducing **potentially antibiotic-resistant organisms**.

Recommendations

1. **Establishment of Cassava Processing Zones:** Cassava mills should be strategically located away from **residential areas, water bodies, and agricultural land** to prevent environmental contamination.
2. **Effluent Treatment Mandates:** Government agencies should enforce **mandatory pre-treatment of cassava mill effluent** before disposal, using cost-effective biological or chemical treatment technologies.
3. **Legislative Framework and Monitoring:** National environmental protection agencies should develop and implement **stringent guidelines** for waste discharge from agro-industrial processing plants, with **routine compliance monitoring**.
4. **Community-Based Education Programs:** Awareness campaigns should be launched to educate farmers and processors on the **ecological dangers of indiscriminate effluent disposal** and best practices for sustainable waste management.

Suggestions for Further Research

To build on the current findings, future studies should:

- a. Assess the **long-term ecological impact** of cassava mill effluent on **aquatic ecosystems** and **groundwater quality**.
- b. Investigate the **horizontal gene transfer potential** of antibiotic resistance among soil microbiota exposed to untreated effluent.
- c. Evaluate the **effectiveness of natural or engineered bioremediation techniques**, such as **microbial consortia** or **phytoremediation**, in detoxifying contaminated soils.
- d. Explore the **public health implications** of chronic exposure to antibiotic-resistant bacteria originating from cassava effluent-affected environments.

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Author Contributions

Aliyu Bello conceptualized the study, designed the methodology, supervised the sample collection and laboratory analysis, and contributed significantly to data interpretation and manuscript drafting. **I.A.A. Ibrahim** carried out the experimental work,

performed statistical analysis, prepared the initial manuscript draft, and contributed to literature review and data visualization.

Danjuma Yakubu performed statistical analysis and prepared the manuscript. All authors critically reviewed and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Conflict of Interest Declaration

The authors declare that **there is no conflict of interest** regarding the conduct, authorship, or publication of this research

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